

Overview of Developed Board Games

- within the Photonics Games competition

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Photonics4All has organised a photonics competition for pupils in schools which resulted in the submission of plenty of high-quality photonics games. The game competition took mainly place in Italy.

The following games are all original board games on light and photonics, realized during the "[Fotonica in Gioco](#)" contest for High School Students in Italy.

If you are interested in playing, purchasing or even replicating one of the following games please do not hesitate to contact the students. They will be happy about your interest in their games!

Are you a physics teacher looking for something to make light and Photonics more interesting for your pupils? Our games invented by students could be perfect for you!

C the speed of light

It's a game which requires concentration, fast hands, but also a bit of strategy and a dash of fortune! You win if you reach first the speed of light... without overtaking it! Are you going to be good enough and know exactly when to stop? Challenge yourself and your friends, have fun and go at the speed of light!

One of the best 10 games of the competition, special mention for the insertion of technological elements in the prototype.

For more Information please contact: Alice Roma: calabresi.r@gmail.com, Liceo Statale A. Manzoni.

Fotonic 2015

The aim of the game is to teach and to make clear a lot of curiosities about this topic, always keeping in mind the fun and the interaction among players, they will have to answer to some questions in order to conquer “The Biggest Bulb of Our Solar System”, our Sun. But pay attention to the “ERRORS” of the Robots: the Universe is a zone still pervaded by obscurity and danger, play FOTONIC 2015 to enlighten it. The final purpose is to arrive on the box of the Sun, moving yourself following the path of the various boxes.

For more Information please contact: Cesare Mercalli: cesare.mercalli@email.it, Liceo Cairoli.

Lampo di Genio

Lampo di Genio is an enthusiastic and educational board game, in which you are a scientist and, before you, you have an enormous view of the Universe and its laws to explore! Your aim is to discover the behaviour of light. Make your discoveries, add your hexagon, pay attention not to lose your resources and be the first one who discovers the Light Theory to win the game!!!

One of the best 10 games of the competition, special mention for the overall high quality.

For more Information please contact: Gualtiero Grassucci:
gualtiero.grassucci@liceograssilatina.org, Liceo Scientifico G.B. Grassi, Liceo Artistico Latina.

Light Finder

“Light Finder” is a journey into the world of Light, which passes through three environments in which the light is treated from the scientific, artistic and entertainment viewpoint. Choose your pawn, you can be Einstein, Newton, Caravaggio, Hawking, Bresson, Curie, Tesla or Dante and across the world as fast as possible. Enjoy Light Finder!

One of the best 10 games of the competition, special mention for fantasy in the realization of the game's elements.

For more information please contact: Mario Di Fonza: mario.difonza@gmail.com, I.S.I.S. “Europa”.

MARAMA

Photonics had never been so entertaining and easy to learn, before! Guide your token through the 5 domains and obtain all the 7 colours. Make your move and have fun!

The **winner game** of the competition!

For more information please contact: Lorenzo Carletti: lorenzo.carletti99@gmail.com, Liceo Leonardo Da Vinci a Jesi.

Quanto e bello

Move along a fantastic coloured track with your counter answering questions on light, in Science and Arts and gain photons! You will find stars, black holes and “energy saving” cards. If you are an expert player you can jump to higher game levels, gaining more and more photons and win!

Enjoy the photons game and become a ray of light!

One of the best 10 games of the competition, special mention for the use of artistic elements.

For more information please contact: Paola Calvi: paola.calvi@tiscali.it, I.I.S “Alessandro Volta”, Liceo Artistico.

Scienziati Fotonici

A new incredible molecule has been discovered, but no one seems able to stabilize it. No one, excepts you. Answer physics questions to gain bonus cards and use photons in order to move your molecule faster. But be careful: other three scientists are trying to achieve the success. Will you be able to be the first?

One of the best 10 games of the competition!

For more information please contact: Luca Fabbian: luca.fabbian@hotmail.it, L.S.S Leonardo Da Vinci.

Win or Back

“Win or Back” is a sort of “snakes and ladders” game, where seven teams try to get to the finish square going through different physical phenomena that can booster or hold their race back. A game to play with friends or classmates. Enjoy!

